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D7.6 Report on the contribution on standardisation end-term

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Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

History

Date	Version number	Change
05.06.2024	0.1	First version – to be reviewed internally by KVC
11.06.2024	0.2	Internal review KVC
14.06.2024	1	A new version with input from the internal reviewers
21.06.2024	1.1	Final version including feedback from the quality team

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable **7.6 Report on the contribution to standardisation (end-term)** identifies and analyses the contribution of ValueCare to existing and future standardisation developments. The report intends to clarify the significance of project results to standardisation in promoting innovation, interoperability and sustainability in health and ICT sectors.

Overall, this deliverable complements the work done in D7.5 providing a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing the adoption and use of standards across technological and knowledge-based results of the project. By addressing barriers and enhancing knowledge processes, this document seeks to foster a culture of standardisation that drives innovation, interoperability and sustainability in European Research and Innovation frameworks. Consequently, it is **addressed to researchers and professionals working in the healthcare and digital sector**, particularly with data and supportive technologies for health. Because of the results, it is also addressed to the **International Consortium for Health Outcomes Measurement (ICHOM) community** and any stakeholder interested to know more about standardisation in research projects.

Concretely, the deliverable has **two main objectives**:

- ▶ **Objective 1.** To explore the knowledge processes necessary for applying standards within the ValueCare project and contributing to existing standards frameworks. This means understanding the steps required to integrate standards into the project and contribute with valuable insights to enhance existing standards when possible.
- ▶ **Objective 2.** To identify the barriers and challenges hindering the adoption of standards. This exploration aims to shed light on why European -produced standards are underutilised and provides insights for the standardisation sector to address these issues effectively.

The **methodology** followed to develop the report is described in section 3 and is based on the actions agreed in the previous version of the report (D7.5) and the steps outlined by the European Standards Association in the publication “Increase the impact of your R&D project integrating standardisation” and the steps suggested by the HSBooster in the service provided to the task leader in charge of standardisation (KVC). Thus, a new **mapping exercise about existing standards** was made in section 4.1.1 complemented with the standards used in the technological and knowledge generated Key Exploitable Results (sections 4.3 and 4.4). This exercise was complemented by activities to foster a **common understanding and strategy on standardisation** among project partners (section 4.1.2). At the same time, different **stakeholders were contacted** (UNE and ICHOM) to explore project contributions to existing and new standards (section 4.1.3).

Finally, the **conclusions with the main barriers** face by project partners, **recommendations** and further steps are described in the section 5. Barriers include a lack of awareness among consortium members, the complexity and bureaucracy of the standardisation process, IPR concerns, and insufficient incentives. To address these challenges, efforts were made to increase awareness through dedicated meetings, although consensus on the best approach for standardisation was not really achieved. There was difficulty in recognising the added value of standardisation. Lessons learnt included the importance of dedicated standardisation tasks, early discussions on potential contributions, the usefulness of the HSbooster service for guidance, and valuable stakeholder engagement, even if tangible results were limited.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AB	Advisory Board
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation
CUD	Create Update Delete
CWAs	Cen Workshop Agreements
D	Deliverable
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
HL7	Health Level Seven
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes Measurement
M	Month
ONC	Office of the National Coordinator for Health Information Technology
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OWASP	Open Web Application Security Project
PIA	Privacy Impact Assessment
SDKs	Software Development Kits
UNE	Spanish Association for Standardisation
VBHC	Value-Based Health Care
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction to the ValueCare project

Healthy ageing along with independent living have become fundamental challenges for Europe as all EU member states (and virtually every country in the world) are experiencing growth in the number and proportion of older persons in their population. Several international organisations (Council of Europe, 2014; International Longevity Centre Brazil, 2014; WHO, 2002) have remarked the importance of the independence, participation and autonomy of older people to remain healthy and, consequently, to ensure their quality of life.

The WHO defines health as "...a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease". The idea of health as the absence of disease has long been considered insufficiently broad and not covering all aspects of health. Unfortunately, it is at present likely unobtainable for many, particularly with the rise in chronic disease and an aging population, with many people with multi-morbidity and frailty who require a coordinated care plan involving numerous health providers, social and other care services. The concept of health promoted by WHO is also hard to measure, is not tailored to the individual and, according to some authors, of limited use for assessing whether a health system is providing value to citizens. Greater acknowledgment of areas of wellbeing providing wider value to older people and those with chronic illnesses, such as societal participation and coping capacity, may allow for a more practical and thorough assessment of value in healthcare, particularly in high-income countries. Shilton et al. (2011) propose a definition of health focussed on giving people the income, education, and power to control their lives, highlighting the role of supportive systems, environments, and policies in enabling health.

In this context, ValueCare's vision of healthy ageing is that any older individual in society can live the best life possible according to what they value, facilitated by access to high quality, person-centred, evidence-based and affordable health and social care services, supported by strong and integrated health and social services. ValueCare partners believe that taking an "enhanced value-based approach" (including not only health but also lifestyle and social care in the concept of value-based care) supported by secure and robust digital technologies will help to achieve this. In addition, the project also considers the job satisfaction and the wellbeing of the health and social service providers. Not only satisfying the Triple Aim; i.e. (i) improving the experience of care (including quality and satisfaction); (ii) improving the health of populations; and (iii) containing and potentially reducing, by means of a better use of the available resources, the per capita cost of care, which mainly focuses on the person's side, but taking also into account the care providers and integrating their satisfaction in the job and wellbeing in order to truly optimize ValueCare's performance.

1.1 Objectives of the project

ValueCare addresses Horizon 2020 Call: SC1-DTH-2018-2020 – Digital transformation in Health and Care. The project aims to deliver personalised integrated (health and social) care services, better outcomes for citizens, improved care experience, improved staff satisfaction and greater efficiency in the use of resources and coordination of care in a setting that ensures trust of users and policy makers regarding data access, protection and sharing and which can be replicated and deployed at large scale in other EU countries. In alignment with the above, ValueCare focuses on the following general objectives:

- ▶ Objective 1. To deliver efficient outcome-based integrated (health and social) care to older people suffering from cognitive impairment, frailty and multiple chronic health conditions to improve their quality of life (and of their families)
- ▶ Objective 2. To contribute to the sustainability of health and social care systems in Europe
- ▶ Objective 3. To provide a secure, scalable and robust digital solution for integrated care

2 Introduction to the deliverable

Deliverable 7.6 **Report on the contribution to standardisation (end-term)** identifies and analyses the contribution of ValueCare to existing standards, and the contribution to the ongoing and future standardisation developments. The report intends to clarify the significance of project results to standardisation in promoting innovation, interoperability and sustainability in health and ICT sectors.

As Europe strides towards its vision of a more integrated and competitive knowledge economy, standardisation emerges as the perfect tool for harmonising practices, enhancing collaboration between European countries and facilitating market access for innovative solutions.

In today's interconnected and rapidly evolving global landscape, standardisation serves as a cornerstone for ensuring compatibility, reliability and quality assurance in products, services and processes. By establishing common frameworks and specifications, standardisation streamlines communication, cooperation and strengthens trust and confidence among market and end-users.

In the dynamic landscape of research and innovation, the adoption of standards involves many benefits across diverse sectors and disciplines. Yet, despite the inherent benefits, the widespread application of standards remains a challenge that needs further exploration.

Overall, this deliverable complements the work done in D7.5 providing a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing the adoption and use of standards across technological and knowledge-based results of the project. By addressing barriers and enhancing knowledge processes, this document seeks to foster a culture of standardisation that drives innovation, interoperability and sustainability in European Research and Innovation frameworks.

2.1 Objectives and scope of the deliverable

- ▶ **Objective 1.** To explore the knowledge processes necessary for applying standards within the ValueCare project and contributing to existing standards frameworks. This means understanding the steps required to integrate standards into the project and contribute with valuable insights to enhance existing standards when possible.
- ▶ **Objective 2.** To identify the barriers and challenges hindering the adoption of standards. This exploration aims to shed light on why European -produced standards are underutilised and provides insights for the standardisation sector to address these issues effectively.

2.2 Relation to other WPs and deliverables

This deliverable is strongly linked with the following work-packages (WPs) and deliverables (Table 1):

Table 1. Deliverable relation with other WPs and deliverables

WP	Deliverable	Relationship
WP2	D2.2 & D2.9 Identify data needed start and end-term.	In D2.2 and D2.9 , authors identified the required data and potential standards to respond to the ValueCare approach. In D7.5, the minimal clerical and clinical data needed were identified and how ValueCare’s contribution to validate some existing questionnaires (translated and validated in real populations) was reported. In the present deliverable, some lessons learnt and suggestions to the ICHOM sets are provided.
WP3	D3.2. Technical Requirements of architecture	In this deliverable (D3.2) the technical requirements of the ValueCare digital architecture were presented aiming to support the use of industry standard application interfaces, or Software Development Kits available for communication among the software and hardware. This supports the greatest possible interoperability with third party hardware. In this sense, the use of standards has been reported in this deliverable to further analyse their exploitation opportunities among the WP7.
	D3.3 Conceptual design	This deliverable defined the overall technical architecture of the ValueCare system. To enhance its exploitation potential, it was crucial to describe how it could be integrated with other systems, either by connecting to them or augmenting them with external functionalities. This approach aimed to maximize the exploitation opportunities within WP7.
	D3.4 ValueCare integration framework	D3.4 detailed the Interoperability Standards for the Healthcare systems. This deliverable focused on the use of the identified standards.
	D3.5 Report on digital solution testing, security and privacy mechanisms	D3.5 provided an overview of the security guidelines and the methodology for the creation of the digital solution. This deliverable focused on data privacy and security standards.
WP4	D4.2 Implementation plan for each pilot site D4.3 Report regarding the implementation	In D4.2, pilots described their plans to implement the ValueCare solution and in D4.3, the implementation process was reviewed. Some pilots included extra questionnaires and instruments according to their target population. All this information is reviewed in the present deliverable to explore how the ValueCare outcomes could contribute to the ICHOM standards and validate other instruments. Concretely, lessons learnt, and suggestions are included in this deliverable.
Wp5	D5.1 Agreed-upon pilot sites evaluation framework D5.2 & D5.3 Intermediate preliminary analyses reports	In D5.1 the common evaluation framework to all ValueCare pilot sites was defined with the questionnaires to be used and further analysed in D5.2& D5.3. As for the WP4, the information included in these deliverables is reviewed in D7.6 to explore how the ValueCare outcomes could contribute to the ICHOM standards and validate other instruments. Concretely, lessons learnt, and suggestions are included in this deliverable.
WP7	D7.5 Report on the contribution to standardisation	D7.5 provides starting information for other WPs, ensuring compatibility and interoperability with what already exists in the market through standards. All this information is reviewed and updated within the present deliverable.
WP8	D8.7, D8.8 Data & D8.9 management	Both D8.7 and D8.8 encompass information on data management during and post-project, as well as the methodologies and standards to be employed. The use of identified standards in D8.7-D8.9 has been examined in the present deliverable.

3 Methodology

The methodology followed in this deliverable is based on the actions outlined in D7.5 and the steps established by European standards organisations in the publication “Increase the impact of your R&D project integrating standardisation” and the steps suggested by the HSBooster in the service provided to the task leader in charge of standardisation (KVC).

3.1 Actions outlined in D7.5

The actions defined in the previous deliverable on standardisation (D7.5) were:

- ▶ To continue with the mapping exercise: health standards, health data standards and technological standards applicable to the ValueCare digital solution. See upload mapping exercise in section 4.1 and 4.3.
- ▶ To explore how ValueCare can contribute to these standards: based on the selected Key Exploitable Results (KERs), KVC asked each responsible partner about the standards used in their development and the potential contribution to existing or new standards.
- ▶ To consult with the project Advisory Board (AB) and relevant stakeholders at European and national level. In particular: the International Consortium for Health Outcomes Measurement (ICHOM) and the Spanish Association for Standardisation (UNE).

Unfortunately, no meetings with national bodies were organised by project partners as planned in D7.5. During the project implementation, some training and awareness activities were developed to spread standardisation knowledge among partners. After gaining a deeper understanding of ValueCare's potential contribution, efforts were centralized in KVC for potential common contributions, such as ICHOM. The decision was made to wait for the final version of the results before exploring how to share them among interested partners and to work on standardisation related to these results, if appropriate. As a final action, once this deliverable is approved by the European Commission, KVC with the support of the partner IFIC will translate the content in a practical and editable format that will be disseminated to the relevant audiences.

3.2 Steps to standardisation

Following the steps established by the HSbooster and the publication “Increase the impact of your R&D project integrating standardisation”, partners developed the following tasks:

1. **Screening of existing standards.**

As advanced previously, in D7.5, partners already identified standards relevant for ValueCare at national, European and international level. In this deliverable, this mapping exercise is complemented in section 4.1 and 4.3.

2. Contribution to new standards.

First, an **internal workshop on exploitation and standardisation** was held during the face-to-face consortium meeting in Athens in 2023. This workshop was organised by KVC and ECHAlliance with the aim of thinking collectively about the potential exploitable outcomes of the ValueCare project and the standardisation opportunities that could be pursued by the consortium. During the workshop, the following questions were raised to the partners:

- ▶ How can the work done in ValueCare Digital Solution contribute to existing standards?
- ▶ Is ValueCare providing new potential standards?
- ▶ Is the ValueCare Digital solution contributing to the digital transition? If yes, how?
- ▶ Can the ValueCare Digital solution be connected/integrated with other solutions/products?
- ▶ Is the ValueCare Digital Solution following existing standards so far?

Although the partners discussed during the meeting, they needed more time to think about these questions and answers were received by email from the coordinator (EMC), the technological partners (FBK) and concept developers (ISRAA).

Beyond this workshop, a **standardisation internal webinar** was organised for project partners with a primary focus on standardisation within the ValueCare project. The objectives of the webinar were twofold: i) to show and discuss the conclusions of the internal workshop; and ii) to address two pivotal questions:

- ▶ How can the work accomplished in the ValueCare project contribute to existing standards?
- ▶ Is the ValueCare project generating new potential standards?

Additionally, a part of the webinar was concentrated on the digital solution, during which the partners involved discussed on several critical questions:

- ▶ Is the ValueCare digital solution contributing to the digital transition? If so, how?
- ▶ Is the ValueCare digital solution capable of being connected to or integrated with other solutions and products?
- ▶ Is the ValueCare digital solution adhering to existing standards, such as those related to AI and security?

Moreover, meetings with **external stakeholders** (ICHOM, UNE and AB) were organised.

Finally, the **HSbooster service on standardisation** was received by KVC. The HSbooster Consultancy Service focuses on providing expert consultancy on various standardisation-related aspects of a given research project. The consultancy aims to enhance the project's understanding and engagement with standardisation processes to achieve effective results. As a result of this service, a set of materials and guidance on how to address this deliverable were received. A total of three sessions were held with the expert of standardisation on 26/04/23; 02/06/2023; and 30/06/2023 following the standard procedure for this service (Figure 1).

Figure 1. HSbooster timeline

4 Standardisation context in R&D projects at European Level

The role of standardisation has traditionally been used for products, services or methods well established in the market, to solve problems related to marketing, safety or compatibility issues. In recent years, standardisation bodies are trying to use it for new products, new methods or technologies to be known and recognised and to generate confidence in users and facilitate market entry.

Numerous rationales underscore the importance of standards and standardisation for researchers, highlighting the potential advantages of adopting standards and engaging in standards development processes through technical committees. However, the synergy among research, industries, and standardisation remains insufficiently documented across various fields, sectors and disciplines, primarily due to a lack of studies. Researchers' awareness and knowledge about standardisation processes is frequently low.

Why integrate standards in Research and Innovation Projects at EU level?

Research project results can be valuable inputs for existing and new standards. In fact, by incorporating the latest knowledge into new standards, can provide the foundation for further developments, new research and ultimately new knowledge (CENELEC).

According to Mijatovic, Tomic and Kicanovic (2022) from the HSbooster.eu training academy, the benefits of using standards in research are the following:

- Ensuring the quality and interoperability of the research process
- Ensuring the research results safety
- Preventing not "reinventing the wheel"
- Promoting common best-practice solutions
- Supporting researchers to achieve common agreements leading to interoperability, compatibility and terminology.
- Enhancing scientific co-operation, networking and learning
- Shaping practices to innovation and research results to innovative technologies, products and services
- Ensuring the commercialisation of research results
- Guarantying the subsequent use of research results
- Supporting the regulatory framework

Moreover, the European Commission and the Council published a series of recommendations related to standards and research that guide researchers and highlight the benefits of contributing to standardisation with the research projects:

- **Council Recommendation (EU) 2022/2415 adopted on 2 December 2022 on guiding principles for knowledge valorisation:** Responds to the needs and feedback of knowledge valorisation actors including policy making and provide a common reference to improve knowledge valorisation in the EU.
- **Commission Recommendation (EU) 2023/498 of 1 March 2023 on a Code of Practice on standardisation in the European Research Area:** It provides a series of recommendations to beneficiaries of public funded research and innovation programmes on how to valorise project results through standards.
- **Commission Recommendation (EU) 2024/774 1 Marc 2024 on Code of Practice on industry-academia co-creation for knowledge valorisation:** It provides practical guidance and tools for research and innovation actors to create an enabling environment and conditions for collaboration.

According to UNE (Webinar on June 2023), research projects can contribute to standards in different ways aligned with their TRL:

Table 2. Contribution to standardisation according to the project TRL

TRL	Potential contribution
TRL ₁ & TRL ₂	Terminology
TRL ₃ , TRL ₄ , TRL ₅	Methods, trials
TRL ₅ , TRL ₆ , TRL ₇	Good practices, Criteria, KPIs, Interoperability, Organisation
TRL ₈ , TRL ₉	Products, services

ValueCare as a project aimed to deliver personalised integrated (health and social) care services can become a solution that can be understood, accepted and applied by the market. The solution has the common agreement of the partners involved in the project and has been tested in 7 pilot sites. The ValueCare health and social pathways are supported by a digital solution that has been based on existing tools/platforms, already developed by the partners FBK, VIDAVO and VI with Technology Readiness Level - TRL 9 besides the HORUS.AI that is currently TRL 7. TRL finally achieved in the ValueCare project is 9.

In sum, ValueCare can contribute to new knowledge (value-based healthcare), new methods (co-design) and supportive technology (digital solution). The ValueCare contribution is further analysed around the identified Key Exploitable Results (KERs) in sections 4.3 and 4.4.

4.1 Standardisation as valorisation of results in European Projects: the ValueCare case

Following the recommendations of the Commission in their Code of Practice on standardisation in the European Research Area, ValueCare partners:

- Included a dedicated task and deliverables on standardisation in the proposal stage.
- Performed an initial analysis of existing standards at European and national level that can be applied to the ValueCare project was made. It was reported in D7.5.
- Explored new standards based on the KERs (tangible and intangible).
- Made contacts along the project implementation with standardisation bodies and relevant actors.
- Defined a common understanding of standardisation along the project implementation thanks to the dedicated meetings and collaborative work.

This procedure has enhanced the project results as well as contributed to its dissemination. In the following sections, a detailed description of the steps performed is provided.

4.1.1 Existing standards landscape

In D7.5, a first mapping of existing standards was carried out to identify and analyse:

- ▶ Existing common standards in health and social care
- ▶ Existing common standards on health
- ▶ Existing common standards at technological level applied to ValueCare digital solution

Moreover, D7.5 provided information about standardisation committees and related organisations:

- ▶ Standardisation bodies at EU level
- ▶ Standardisation bodies at National level

As mentioned in the methodology, partners continued with this mapping exercise to explore new **initiatives which could be interesting for the ValueCare project**. Some initiatives focused on **active aging**. Active ageing standardisation in Europe involves the development and implementation of standards aimed at promoting and supporting well-being, inclusion and participation of older individuals in various facets of life. These standards encompass a wide range of areas, including health care, social services, technology with the overarching goal of fostering an age-friendly environment. The European Committee for Standardisation (CEN) and the European Committee for

Electrotechnical Standardisation (CENELEC) actively contribute to the standardisation process in this domain. They engage experts, stakeholders, and organizations to collaboratively develop standards that address the challenges and opportunities associated with active ageing. These standards not only focus on improving the quality of life for older adults but also contribute to creating a more supportive and accessible society for individuals of all ages. Key aspects of active ageing standardisation in Europe include the establishment of guidelines for age-friendly products and services, the development of interoperable and user-friendly technologies, and the promotion of inclusivity in various sectors. Furthermore, these standards emphasise the importance to consider diverse needs and abilities, ensuring that solutions are adaptable and tailored to the dynamic and evolving requirements of an ageing population. No new standards were identified in this field, but partners explored other standards that can be also applied to ValueCare as those related to health informatics and accessibility.

Regarding **health informatics**, CEN/TC 251 “Classification of purposes for processing personal health information (ISO/TS 14265:2024)” establishes high-level categories for processing personal health information, including its collection, use, storage, access, analysis, creation, linking, communication, disclosure, and retention. These categories provide a framework to classify specific purposes defined by healthcare organisations, regional health authorities, jurisdictions, or countries. This framework aids in the consistent management of information for healthcare services delivery and the communication of electronic health records (EHR) across organisational and jurisdictional boundaries. Additionally, **82304-2 standard**, "Health and wellness apps – Quality and reliability," is an international standard that specifies the requirements for the quality and reliability of health and wellness applications. This standard ensures that such apps meet certain criteria to provide safe, effective, and reliable services to users. It encompasses different aspects of app development, including the design, testing, validation, and maintenance processes, to guarantee that the apps are robust and fit for their intended purpose. Finally, **17975 standard**, "Health informatics – Principles and requirements for electronic consent," is a new international standard that outlines the principles and requirements for the electronic consent process. This standard aims to ensure that electronic consent forms, such as those used in the GemsTracker process¹, are secure, user-friendly, and legally compliant. It covers the design, implementation, and management of electronic consent systems, to facilitate clear and informed consent from users. The standard addresses issues such as data privacy,

¹ Gemstraker is the tool used in the project to store the data collected from the questionnaires. It is a platform that allows not only to evaluation of the process for electronic informed consent but also the collection and management of data from the questionnaires related to each electronic informed consent.

security, transparency, and user understanding to ensure that the electronic consent process is reliable and trustworthy.

Accessibility standards focus on making products, services, and environments accessible to older adults and individuals with disabilities, for example:

- ▶ ISO 21542: "Building construction -- Accessibility and usability of the built environment"
- ▶ ISO 9241-171: "Ergonomics of human-system interaction -- Part 171: Guidance on software accessibility"
- ▶ EN 301 549: "Accessibility requirements suitable for public procurement of ICT products and services in Europe"

Although the first standard is out of the scope since it deals with built environment, the others can be related with the digital solution developed to support older people in the care pathways.

In the case of Ireland, partners provided the following National Standards for the entity already identified in D7.5, the National Standards Authority of Ireland (NSAI) (Table 3)

Table 3. Certifications applied to health and social care in Ireland

Health sector	NSAI National Committees
Medical device	NSAI TC 5 – Healthcare Standard Committees NSAI ETC/TC 10 – Electrical equipment in medical practice
Health informatic	NSAI/TC 21 – Health Informatics
Healthcare	NSAI/TC 152 – Healthcare services

4.1.2 Common understanding and strategy on standardisation

As mentioned in the methodology section, a **consortium workshop** regarding the roadmap towards standardisation was conducted, focusing on leveraging the project's results and their contribution to standards, while also addressing the partner's strategic motivation in this field. The workshop yielded some preliminary conclusions guided by the following strategic questions:

▶ **How can the work done in ValueCare Digital Solution contribute to existing standards?**

Through:

- The use of the ICHOM set to assess patient-reported outcome measures among older people with various chronic conditions;
- The implementation of a personalised care plan by integrating standard measures from the medical and social domain;
- The exchange of data through the ValueCare technical solution

▶ **Is ValueCare providing new potential standards?**

ValueCare can be seen as a 'use case' on how data can be exchanged by using common terminology and common data models. Partners were uncertain whether they could support new standards or only contribute to existing ones.

▶ **Is the ValueCare Digital solution contributing to the digital transition? If yes, how?**

Yes. It contributes to the digital transition by enabling a series of actions that otherwise would not be possible such as:

- Increased accessibility to healthcare services regarding time and location (i.e. continuous access to people in rural environments or distant to care facilities).
- Improved patient outcomes, through longitudinal monitoring, personalised recommendations and continuous collection of patients data accessible to care professionals
- Increased engagement and awareness, by empowering patients to take an active role in their healthcare management through the use of the digital tools
- Improving the digital literacy, through the experiencing and use of the digital tools for health

▶ **Can the ValueCare Digital solution be connected/integrated with other solutions/products?**

- Yes. Being developed in three main modules (the web dashboard, the mobile app and the virtual coach engine), the ValueCare system and its components could be interfaced to other solutions and products to enhance its potential use. Moreover, the ValueCare app is highly configurable to tackle other clinical conditions beyond the ones defined within the project pilots.

▶ **Is the ValueCare Digital Solution following existing standards so far?**

- Yes. The design of the digital solution follows the accessibility and security standards such as the ones implemented in the Vidavo dashboard. Moreover, the virtual coach is designed in a compatible way with the approach defined by Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) for healthcare data exchange.

These conclusions were shared and discussed in a **dedicated webinar** with the partners involved in the task. The webinar aimed to: (i) present and discuss the outcomes of the internal workshop, and (ii) address two crucial questions:

► **How can the work achieved in the ValueCare project contribute to existing standards?**

- In D2.2 (p. 30-3) several international standards and standardisation methods ValueCare can learn from and contribute to were outlined. More specifically, ValueCare can contribute to:

1) the use of the ICHOM set to assess patient-reported outcome measures among older people with various chronic conditions. In this sense, for enhancing the interpretation of assessment scores, it will be pertinent to explore the familiarity of healthcare professionals with the assessment instruments used across different pilot sites. This would include understanding whether the scoring methods are commonly understood and how to effectively communicate these scores to patients.

2) the implementation of a personalised care plan by integrating standard measures from the medical and social domain. ValueCare employs the ICHOM as a foundation to understand the health and social outcomes that are significant to the patient. The assessment results are reviewed, and a Personalized Care Plan is formulated, including patient-reported outcomes in both medical and social health domains.

3) the exchange of data through the ValueCare technical solution. The solution facilitates data exchange by ensuring that assessment results, based on ICHOM standard sets, are accessible to all health and social care services. The ValueCare dashboard provides an overview of these assessment results and can be used by health and social service professionals from various organisations.

- It could determine a clear Value-based Health Care (VBHC) pathway method by the adoption of MetroMapping tool².

► **Is the ValueCare project creating new potential standards?**

- Training for VBHC Delivery. Through rounds of co-design and implementation phases, we identified a comprehensive set of skills necessary for healthcare professionals.

² The metromapping tool is a visual and strategic tool designed to map out the landscape of a particular sector, project, or process. It typically represents a comprehensive view of different elements and their interconnections. In the ValueCare project, metromapping served as an assessment tool for evaluating the ValueCare solution. It employed a formula inspired by the Porter model to calculate value. Practitioners responsible for implementing the ValueCare solution rated various elements on a scale ranging from 1 to 5.

- Structured patient discussions. Implementing motivational interviewing skills in patient interactions presented an intriguing avenue for enhancing patient engagement. For instance, in Greece, additional questionnaires within VIDA24 facilitated data collection and interpretation, providing patients with comprehensive reports post-evaluation. However, emphasis should be placed on refining the approach to effectively motivate and engage patients during discussions.
- Standardisation relevant to this project pertains more to specific guidelines and processes for developing the application rather than the application itself. Technical partners have applied the 82304-2 standard (health and wellness apps – quality and reliability) and Open Web Application Security Project (OWASP) guidelines as much as possible; and they follow the Agile process. They have not drafted detailed guidelines on the development of the digital solution, but a brief overview would be necessary.

Finally, the following **next steps** were agreed during the webinar:

- ▶ To do a preliminary evaluation on how the ValueCare project can contribute to standards (standardisation improvement) such as:
 - 17975 standard - new standard on the evaluation of the process for electronic consent form (Gemstraker) – how data is collected in the electronic consent forms. Included in the mapping exercise.
 - 82304-2 standard -health and wellness apps – quality and reliability. Included in the mapping exercise and used in the mobile health app.
- ▶ To schedule meetings with standardisation bodies based on the ideas collected. As detailed, KVC organized meetings with UNE.
- ▶ Standardisation as a tool for dissemination of project results and interaction with market stakeholders. In this point, as advanced in the methodology, partners agreed to have the final approved version of this deliverable prior to disseminate it by IFIC to relevant audiences.
- ▶ The training on VBHC was agreed to be an action to explore after the project duration. This KER is detailed in section 4.4.

4.1.3 Stakeholder involvement

As mentioned in the methodology section, partners consulted the AB about their impressions on how ValueCare can contribute to standards. Their suggestion was to focus on the knowledge generated instead of focusing on the digital solution. Additionally, two main contacts were made during the project implementation:

Meeting with **UNE** (Spanish Association for Standardisation) to gain insights into the standardisation processes of CEN-CENELEC and the Cen Workshop Agreements (CWAs). The objective of the meeting was to deepen our understanding of how these organisations establish and maintain standards, with a particular focus on the processes and steps involved. By engaging UNE, ValueCare has gathered valuable knowledge that has informed our own standardisation efforts and contributed to the alignment of further activities with standardisation efforts. The possibility to create a CWA was explored and finally not taken as partners need to advance in the standardisation process before to take a decision on which topic can be submitted to a CWA once the KERs are decided and their contribution to existing or new standards is clear.

Meeting with **ICHOM**, as key reference on promoting value-based healthcare by defining global standard sets. These standards set helps healthcare providers and organisations measure, report and improve patient outcomes effectively. ValueCare project has used ICHOM questionnaires with healthcare professionals and patients and engaged Mona Kahlid as chair of the Advisory Board as key expert on ICHOM. In particular, ValueCare partners were interested in contributing to:

- ▶ The ICHOM data set of older people with the ValueCare questionnaires implemented in all the pilot sites.
- ▶ The ICHOM Stroke set in the case of Rotterdam Pilot
- ▶ The ICHOM Diabetes in the case of the Athens Pilot.

In this sense, ValueCare project has endeavoured to enrich such questionnaires with the lessons learned and best practices from the interventions conducted within the project activities, by integrating insights and experiences the aim was to enhance the comprehensiveness and relevance of the outcome questionnaires defined by ICHOM. A dedicated meeting was held with one member of ICHOMs (project manager) to explore how ValueCare can contribute with the lessons learnt and validated translated versions. Unfortunately, this collaborative effort was finally not possible due to the internal procedures of ICHOM organisation that does not collect translated versions of the questionnaires nor lessons learnt. The project manager suggested that we can share our lessons learnt in a dedicated scientific publication and share this with them in their repositories. This will be explored

once the analyses in WP5 are finalised. In the meanwhile, ValueCare partners involved in the pilot sites using the ICHOM sets would like to share their lessons learnt and suggestions in this deliverable:

Table 4. ICHOM lessons learnt and suggestions

Lessons learnt	Suggestions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support older people to answer the questionnaire by his/her informal caregiver or by the researchers in charge of the study. - Engage the health and social staff. - Increase awareness among patients, careers and healthcare professionals. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To facilitate validated translated version of the questionnaires. - Reduce the number of items in each set, or at least identified the ones that are more relevant. - Try to avoid reiterative questions. - Align the questionnaire with the items that the health professionals had internally in their Electronic Health Records. - To clarify older people questions that could be confusing for them. For example, regarding the comorbidities.

4.2 ValueCare HSbooster experience

KVC, as partner in charge of the standardisation, asked for the HSbooster service. The HSbooster service consists of a series of formative webinars for projects, along with instructional documentation. The focus of these sessions was to increase our understanding how the team can adopt current standards and best practices (at health, care and technology level) as well as understanding how the results of the project could inform or influence existing standardisation working groups.

The service has been instrumental in guiding the initial phases of the project deliverable and knowledge regarding results standardisation. The support received from the expert has been outstanding. Right from the beginning, he has been attentive, meeting expectations in our interactions and facilitating collaborative work, project dissemination, fostering synergies and enhancing awareness among R&D projects and people.

Three meetings were held:

- ▶ In the first meeting (26/04/23) an overview of the service was provided by the HSbooster and KVC presented the ValueCare project on how the standardisation is envisioned (see annex 1).
- ▶ During the second and third meetings (02/06/2023 and 30/06/2023) the expert provided advice on specific actions that ValueCare partners could implement to advance in the standardisation of project results. In these meetings, learning materials were exchanged and analysed. KVC also presented the index of the current D7.6 to guarantee the focus is aligned with the research projects standardisation roadmaps. In particular:
 - Analysis of the existing standards landscape (section 4.1, 4.3 and 4.4)

- Activities to establish common knowledge of standards and a strategic position on this (internal workshop and webinar)
- Involving partners with standardisation experience (UNE)
- Making standards a tangible part of the project (in relation to KERs)
- Suitable and realistic outputs, outcomes and impact key performance indicators on standards and standardisation.

In the Description of Action (DoA), the following indicators were included in relation to standardisation (Table 5):

Table 5. KPIs related with standardisation included in the Description of Action

KPI	Mean of verification	Achieved?
KPI: Availability of valid instruments, able to improve the quality of life, life satisfaction, loneliness and social isolation	Self-reported and collaboratively reported	ICHOM data set for older people was completed by a total of circa 1680 participants (240 in each pilot site). At the time of writing, WP5 is still analysing the data.
KPI: Standardisation of data gathering procedures: (1) ontologies, (2) interoperability of data	Project final report	The standards used in the digital solution (within the different components) are described in section 4.3 of this deliverable. The final report will be delivered at the end of the project, so it is not available at the time of writing.
KPI: Standardisation of cybersecurity and privacy protection technologies specifically for disruptive technologies based on massive data mining and analysis.		

- Finally, the expert summarised the activities performed and recommended future actions. Additional suggestions and feedback were provided via email. Below, the feedback provided by the expert:

"The project is actively looking for ways to address the need to link with standardisation activities. These have mainly two routes. First, understanding how the team can adopt current standards and best practices, at both levels of health and care, and technology. Second, understanding how the results of the project could inform or influence existing standardisation working groups.

After the first and second meetings, it is clear the next activities the project should take as a follow-up.

The project should continue the good progress in the implementation aligned with the standards already identified for the PREMs/PROMs for their use cases (e.g. ICHOM). Additionally, the technical partners should consider the application of mentioned standards from the technical domain, mainly available from ISO, IEC, ITU and IEEE.

Such information, as well as some link related to an example of a standardisation process, as it happens in IEEE, has been shared during video conference meetings and by asynchronous communication.

This part would correspond to the first route, and may well identify challenges, barriers or opportunities that can substantiate the second route to contribute to standardisation.

The second route may be well achieved with the forthcoming deliverable, expected to May 2024³. A possible structure for the document was worked on during the provision of this service and shall serve as a guideline for collecting meaningful content that could be shared with the related SDO WGs. For example, one of the most wanted contributions from standardisation groups is the reference to adoption examples, use cases and concrete approaches trying to use a given standard. Any insight on the difficulties and practicalities of adopting a standard is most welcome by the WGs that can open new projects for either extending or updating new standards or creating new standards covering other aspects of a specific domain that might not be well addressed by current means.

Therefore, it is advised that the team should maintain the work considering these two potential routes for exploring the project results, plus the potential participation in SDO WGs that are open for individual participation. Furthermore, it is advised that the relevant parts of the deliverable that is being prepared could be shared with the community in the form of one or several open-access papers”.

Following the suggestions received by the HSbooster expert, KVC explored synergies with UNE and ICHOM (as described in the section 4.1.3). Also, as described in the methodology section, once the current deliverable is approved by the European Commission, KVC will translate the content in a practical and editable format that will be disseminated with the support of IFIC to the relevant audiences. Following the expert advice, this publication will be open access. This publication does not avoid the potential publications of partners along the project implementation and after highlighting their contributions to standards, barriers and challenges. All these publications will follow the open access format as they are derived from a European funded project.

4.3 Technological KERS

The ValueCare project aims to provide tools and methods to deliver efficient outcome-based care for older adults, enhancing their quality of life and that of their caregivers while promoting the sustainability of European health and social care systems. To achieve this, the project implements a comprehensive framework addressing both organisational aspects of outcome-based care and the **technological tools necessary to support it**. In this sense, the ValueCare digital solution was

³ Because the extension of the project, the deliverable is expected in June 2024.

developed to empower patients in managing their own health and to assist healthcare professionals and informal caregivers in delivering high-quality care more efficiently. With this aim, the ValueCare solution includes:

- ▶ **A Web Platform:** For professionals to register patients, setting personalised care objectives and interventions, and enabling clinical professionals and authorised caregivers to monitor daily patient progress.
- ▶ **A Mobile App:** For patients to track their goal progress, access educational materials, and communicate with caregivers.
- ▶ **A Virtual Coach:** Embedded in the mobile app, it provides motivational feedback, reminders, and targeted interventions to help patients adhere to their personalized care plans.

The following picture (Figure 2) represents the integration of the different components of the digital solution (extracted from D3.3 “Conceptual Design”)

Figure 2. ValueCare Concept driven by value-based requirements

These components are integrated to comply with regulatory requirements (such as GDPR) and are tailored to support patients with various diseases, following a unified, value-based approach focused on specific health outcomes as determined by each pilot site involved in the ValueCare project.

Thus, ValueCare digital solution contributes to the **digital transition** by:

- ▶ increasing accessibility to healthcare services regarding time and location (i.e. continuous access to people in rural environments or distant to care facilities),
- ▶ improving patient outcomes, through longitudinal monitoring, personalised recommendations and continuous collection of patients data accessible to health professionals, and

- ▶ improving digital literacy, through the experiencing and use of the digital tools for health.

In this sense, standardisation in ValueCare project can be linked to the guidelines and processes for the development of the digital solution rather than to the application itself. Of particular significance within the procedures followed, is the emphasis on facilitating interactions among technology developers, patients, and healthcare professionals. Training is key in these procedures as it serves to bridge the gap between technical and non-technical stakeholders, providing essential insights into technological tools. This shared understanding fosters a common language, known as HEALTH-TECH, facilitating effective communication and collaboration, in this sense, standardising vocabulary ensures clarity and coherence, particularly in conveying potential outcomes to patients. While standards to build web applications and mobile backends have been established for many years, their alignment with healthcare practices remains underdeveloped. Therefore, integrating healthcare-specific standards into the development process is crucial for ensuring the application's effectiveness and relevance within the healthcare domain.

Why apply standards for the ValueCare Technological KERs?

The application of standards to the technological KERs is essential for ensuring quality, enhancing interoperability, facilitating market entry, fostering innovation, and managing intellectual property. By adhering to standards, ValueCare maximises the impact of their technological innovations, ensuring that they are reliable, compatible, and market ready. This approach not only enhances the success of the project but also contributes to the broader advancement of technology and industry.

Standards provide a benchmark for quality and performance, ensuring that the technological KERs developed within a project meet specific criteria for **safety, reliability, and efficiency**. This is particularly important in fields such as healthcare, where the stakes for product performance are high. Adhering to standards helps maintain consistency in the development process, leading to more predictable and reliable outcomes and minimise risks associated with new technologies, since many standards include guidelines for safety and regulatory compliance.

Interoperability is the ability of different systems and technologies to work together seamlessly. Standards play a critical role in ensuring that technological KERs can integrate with existing systems and other new technologies. On the one hand, they ensure that new technologies can communicate and function effectively with other systems, enhancing their usability and adoption. On the other hand, projects that follow interoperability standards can more easily integrate their innovations into larger, more complex systems, increasing the value and applicability of their KERs.

Interoperability within healthcare systems is crucial for facilitating seamless information exchange across regional, national, and organisational boundaries. Healthcare interoperability encompasses

application interfaces, data exchange, and secure data sharing among various healthcare stakeholders. As detailed in D3.4, there are four levels of interoperability:

- ▶ **Foundational (Level 1):** This level establishes the basic requirements for systems or applications to securely communicate and exchange data with one another.
- ▶ **Structural (Level 2):** At this level, interoperability defines the format, syntax, and organization of data exchange, including specifications at the data field level for effective interpretation.
- ▶ **Semantic (Level 3):** Semantic interoperability involves the use of common underlying models and standardised data elements, ensuring that data is codified using publicly available value sets and coding vocabularies. This fosters a shared understanding and meaning among users.
- ▶ **Organisational (Level 4):** Organisational interoperability encompasses governance, policy, social, legal, and organisational considerations. It ensures secure, seamless, and timely communication and data usage within and between organisations, entities, and individuals. Components such as shared consent, trust, and integrated end-user processes and workflows are essential for achieving organisational interoperability.

These four levels of interoperability collectively enable effective communication and data sharing across the healthcare ecosystem, promoting improved care coordination, patient outcomes, and overall healthcare delivery. In this sense, the three industry standards that played a pivotal role in establishing foundational and structural interoperability within the ValueCare project were:

- ▶ **Consolidated Clinical Document Architecture (C-CDA):** Developed collaboratively by Health Level Seven (HL7), Integrating the Healthcare Environment (IHE), the Health Story Project, and Office of the National Coordinator for Health Information Technology (ONC), C-CDA facilitates the creation of clinical documents containing both human-readable text and machine-readable Extensible Markup Language (XML) format, as per ONC guidelines.
- ▶ **DirectTrust:** It is a collaborative, non-profit industry alliance that promotes health data exchange using the direct message standard. Like C-CDA, DirectTrust uses a document-based exchange approach.
- ▶ **Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR)⁴:** Developed and maintained by HL7, FHIR is an internet-based data standard designed to connect various discrete data elements. FHIR has rapidly gained popularity and has become one of the most widely adopted standards for enabling structural, and in some cases, semantic interoperability. The widespread adoption of FHIR by major Electronic Health Records vendors has contributed to its prominence as a leading method for data exchange.

⁴ <https://hl7.org/FHIR/>

Standards play a crucial role in enabling interoperability between systems and devices by providing a common language and set of expectations. These standards are developed and maintained by standards organizations, which focus on producing standards to address the needs of a wide base of adopters. Two widely supported standards for healthcare system interoperability are **ISO/CEN EN 13606** and **HL7 FHIR**. In ValueCare, we focused on the HL7 FHIR.

HL7, or Health Level Seven, encompasses a set of international standards for the transfer of clinical and administrative data between software applications used by healthcare providers.

FHIR, or Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources, is a standard for health data exchange published by HL7. FHIR combines the best features of previous HL7 standards while leveraging web standards and focusing on implementability. It facilitates the exchange of healthcare information between organisations through resources that describe exchangeable health data formats and elements, as well as standardisation for application programming interfaces (APIs). FHIR offers several benefits, including interoperable exchange with legacy standards, lower overhead, shorter learning curve, selective transmission of information, potential for patient-mediated data, and a supportive community of implementers. The development of HL7 FHIR was driven by the need for connected care, allowing access and exchange of health information among different healthcare facilities, professionals, and patients without overwhelming message traffic. Interoperability standards are individual standards harmonised and integrated to meet specific healthcare and business needs for sharing information among organisations and systems. HL7 FHIR, designed with the complexity of healthcare data in mind, takes a modern, internet-based approach to connect discrete elements through modular components called "Resources," which share common features such as a URL, metadata, human-readable summary, defined data elements, and an extensibility framework.

In relation to data, the ValueCare approach aims to facilitate **data exchange** using standardised terminology and common data models. As detailed in D2.2, the following standards have been used during the project:

- ▶ **Use of Standardised Terminology.** The international standard for clinical terminology is SNOMED CT⁵. This standard enhances communication and the availability of relevant clinical information among care providers, such as within Electronic Health Records. SNOMED CT is compatible with other international medical classification systems, like ICD-10, and allows for the addition of new concepts, descriptions, and relationships to its logical model. At the national level, the implementation and adoption of SNOMED CT by health care and IT suppliers must be

⁵ <https://www.snomed.org/>

supported. In the Netherlands, for instance, the Nictiz (Dutch National Knowledge Institute on Digital Data Exchange in Care) facilitates implementation through the SNOMED National Release Center by providing free licenses, courses, and advice. Additionally, national guidelines for medical professionals are integrated into the SNOMED CT standard in the Netherlands.

- ▶ **Use of Observational Data from Various Sources with Common Data Models.** The Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) community is engaged in standardising databases worldwide. They focus on the development and adoption of the OMOP Common Data Model. Different data sources, such as administrative systems and EHR, can be converted to the OMOP model. Subsequently, analytic tools can be used to derive evidence from these standardised data. This evidence serves multiple purposes, including research and insurance claims.

Moreover, for new technologies to be **commercially successful**, they must often meet certain standards to gain market acceptance and comply with regulatory requirements. For example, in the healthcare systems, compliance with recognised standards can be a prerequisite for entering to the market and for ensuring to the consumers and stakeholders that the technology is of high quality and safe to use, thus facilitating market adoption.

Additionally, the application of standards can stimulate **innovation** by providing a common framework within which new ideas can be developed and shared. They enable collaboration among different stakeholders, including researchers, developers, and industry partners.

The framework facilitated the use of industry-standard application interfaces, also known as **Software Development Kits (SDKs)**, to enable communication between software and hardware components. This architecture enabled: i) the seamless integration between the Virtual Coach and vida24 platforms, and ii) the incorporation of activity tracker devices using either the SDK (Beurer AS 99) or the API (for Xiaomi band devices). Additionally, the potential for future connectivity with third-party systems was explored in D3.4 "ValueCare integration framework including definitions of the API FHIR".

Finally, applying standards also plays a crucial role in the management and protection of Intellectual Property Rights associated with technological KERs. Standards can help define the scope and application of patents and other Intellectual Property Rights. Standards can not only guide the development process in a way that protects Intellectual Property Rights, ensuring that innovations are legally safeguarded and can be commercially exploited without infringement, but also provide clarity on the Intellectual Property landscape, helping project teams understand where their innovations fit within existing patents and how they can differentiate their products.

ValueCare Technological KERs and used existing standards

In the following lines, the digital solution of ValueCare is described as well as the standards use in the different components:

▶ **Technological KER 1: Integrated ValueCare Platform**

- **Development leader:** Vodafone Innovus
- **Outcome:** WP₃
- **Description of the KER:** The ValueCare integrated platform encompasses an infrastructure that facilitates interaction among the different components of the ValueCare system, including the web dashboard, the mobile application, and the virtual coach. This platform enables the interconnection of these modules with repositories where patients' data are stored and maintained.
- **Standards:** since the different components of the platforms are detailed in the following lines, all the mentioned standards also apply to the whole Integrated ValueCare Platform. Moreover, the Agile Process was followed for all the Platform components. Agile process for software development emphasizes continuous collaboration with end-users and improvement of the software to be developed.

▶ **Technological KER 2: Web Dashboard**

- **Development leader:** VIDAVO
- **Outcome:** WP₃
- **Description of the KER:** The ValueCare includes a dashboard for clinicians to register and monitor patients' progress over time.
- **Standards:**
 - ISO 13485:2016, an essential standard aiming to ensure the quality and safety of medical devices, facilitating international market access and customer trust. Implementing this standard demonstrates a commitment to quality and regulatory compliance in the medical device industry.
 - ISO 9001:2015, which provides a framework to ensure they meet customer and regulatory requirements while striving for continuous improvement. Implementing this standard helps to improve operational efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance customer satisfaction.
 - Regarding security and privacy mechanisms for the web dashboard are detailed in table 6:

Table 6. Web dashboard security and privacy mechanisms

Guidelines/ Mechanisms	
1	The system must use only the required packages and services. Those not required should be removed from the system
2	No interactive login accounts should be used.
3	The data transport between systems is over encrypted protocols only.
4	All components should be updated to the latest security patch.
5	Patches are tested at testing environment before production
6	The authenticated user should be informed of the latest login date.
7	Granted privileges should be the least needed privileges.
8	Each user is granted a unique key during the application lifecycle.
9	All users are required to have complex passwords, one way encrypted at the database (SHA, bcrypt etc)
10	Access of users should be recorded, audit logs with the level access and systems requested
11	Data transmission use checksums to ensure data integrity
12	Creative Update Delete (CUD) operations shall ensure that no intermediate stage takes place that leads to data integrity problems.
13	No production data is transferred between testing environment and production environment.
14	Where pseudo anonymisation methods are used the technical and organisational measures are in place to ensure the separation of such data using an identification key that mitigates the risk of unauthorised reversal of pseudo anonymisation
15	Application interfaces that are accessible from zones with lower security level are accessed via a secure communication channel.
16	The API must not separate data storage, only the existing's infrastructure data storage shall be used.
	Respective Privacy Impact Assessments (PIAs) and Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) are in place:
17	Even though no personal data are collected, still data related to a person exist in the system; those will be retained only for the time that is required.
18	Data that can be used to identify a patient behaviour will be stored only for the project's duration and/or applicable law.

19	Security measures and policies that cover privacy and protection of one's personal identity shall comply with relevant legislation and regulation shall be defined and implemented.
20	All data access, destruction and retention actions shall be executed according to applicable legislation

► **Technological KER 3: Mobile Health App**

- **Development leader:** Vodafone Innovus
- **Outcome:** WP3
- **Description of the KER:** The mobile application offers various self-tracking features and has the capacity to host other components, such as the virtual coach, which empowers patients in the self-management of their prescribed health-related tasks. It provides access to various functionalities including browsing certified educational multimedia materials, access to clinical professionals, statistics about care path compliance and access to the personalised virtual coach.
- **Standards:**
 - CEN ISO - TS82304-21. By adhering to the guidelines and requirements of this standard, technical partners in charge enhanced the quality and reliability of the Mobile Health app, ultimately improving user trust and satisfaction. This technical specification ensured that the app was safe, effective, and capable of delivering valuable health information and support to users.
 - ISO 27001. Using this standard, Vodafone partners systematically and effectively managed their information security risks, enhancing their resilience against security threats, and demonstrating their commitment to protecting sensitive information. This standard is widely recognized and helps build trust with stakeholders by ensuring that robust information security practices are in place.
 - OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development). By using the guidelines and principles of OECD, technological partners contribute to the harmonization across different countries. They are not standards in the formal sense but provide a comprehensive and widely accepted basis for policy-making and regulatory frameworks.
 - OWASP, to improve the security of the app. OWASP's community-driven approach ensures that its tools and guidelines remain relevant and up-to-date with the latest security threats and trends.

- Moreover, during the design and development of the mobile application, the ISO 82304-2 was taken into consideration as a guideline. The following requirements regarding health and safety were taken from ISO 82304-2 specifications (table 7):

Table 7: ISO 82304-2 specifications used in ValueCare

ISO specification/ requirement	
Quality requirements	Health and safe
	Easy to use
	Secure data
	Robust build
Intended Use	Inform, Simple Monitoring, Communicate, Research
Is a medical device?	No. Requirements and usage of the application don't include any feature that could be identified as a medical device.
Are health professionals involved in the development of the health app?	Yes
Health benefit	The mobile application is a companion to the patient and a bridge between the patient and the health care professional.
Usefulness	The mobile application is developed using simple and easy to understand interaction with the end user. It uses pale colors, easy to understand screen flows and targets the least amount of navigation steps.
Support documentation	The mobile application is supported by documents – guidelines and videos.

- Guidelines and mechanisms for ensuring security and privacy of the Mobile Health App are detailed in the following table (Table 8):

Table 8. Mobile Health App security and privacy mechanisms

Guidelines/ Mechanisms	
1	In the design phase, classify data storage according to sensitivity using the Information Security Classification & Protection, and apply controls accordingly.
2	Auto Correction and Autosuggestion for sensitive data input.
3	Don't allow third party keyboard to be used for inputs. Use custom keyboard.
4	Introduce input field masking for sensitive data e.g., password
5	Disable application logging, debug messages at production release.
6	The mobile application runs with the minimum privileges required on the operating system.

7	Passwords are encrypted and biometric only available for auto login. Biometric data are not transported to the server.
8	The mobile application can accept security and bug fixing updates.
9	Authorisation tokens are time limited and auto expire.
10	Authorisation tokens use latest encryption methodologies of the highest possible entropy.
11	Data transfer between server and mobile application is based on TLS certificates.
12	The mobile application doesn't store any personal information on the device of any type.
13	The mobile application uses the latest components and build software versions.
14	During testing the mobile application is decompiled to reveal vulnerabilities.
15	The application won't exchange any data with other applications.
16	The application must be protected from end user injections.
17	During removal of the application no sensitive data is kept or cached.

► **Technological KER 4: Virtual Coaching Semantic-enabled Digital Solution**

- **Development leader:** FBK
- **Outcome:** WP3
- **Description of the KER:** It is a personalized tool aimed at facilitating interactive dialogues between the end-user and an AI-enabled coach, integrating both hybrid, knowledge-based technologies (evidence-based content) and data-driven technologies (patterns of app usage). This tool supports the achievement of a tailored care pathway for each individual.
- **Standards:**
 - The Virtual Coach is designed in a compatible way with the approach defined by the FHIR for health care data exchange. It is the framework for the next generation of the HL7 based and combining the best characteristics of previous HL7 versions and the clinical document architecture.
 - Regarding security and privacy mechanisms, the Virtual Coach was developed in accordance with OWASP techniques, which are considered best practices in the field of security vulnerability prevention. When properly applied, these techniques can significantly reduce the risk of data breaches resulting from software code deficiencies. Guidelines and mechanisms for the security and privacy of the Virtual Coach are detailed in the following table (Table 9):

Table 9. Virtual Coach security and privacy mechanisms

Guidelines/ Mechanisms	
1	The Virtual Coach module doesn't store any personal information on the dashboard and all data is anonymized
2	The Virtual Coach module uses the latest components and libraries versions
3	The Virtual Coach communicates through RabbitMQ ⁶ through AMQP protocol
4	RabbitMQ is configured to use AMQP based on TLS certificates.

The documentation used for RabbitMQ TLS configuration can be found in this [link](#). This guide covers various topics related to TLS in RabbitMQ, with a focus on client connections:

- o Two ways of using TLS for client connections: direct or via a TLS terminating proxy
- o Erlang/OTP requirements for TLS support
- o Enabling TLS in RabbitMQ
- o How to generate self-signed certificates for development and QA environments with `tls-gen` or manually
- o TLS configuration in Java and .NET clients
- o Peer (certificate chain) verification of client connections or mutual ("mTLS")
- o Public key usage extensions relevant to RabbitMQ
- o How to control what TLS version and cipher suite are enabled

D.3.2 "Technical Requirements of Architecture" detailed several system components that contribute to data standardisation in ValueCare, ensuring that the final solution is interoperable and integrated with other data sources and open platforms:

► **Database:**

- The virtual coach database uses **MongoDB**, a NoSQL database known for its high availability and scalable performance.
- Vida24 employs **MySQL**, an open-source relational database management system (RDBMS), to store health and wellbeing data from ValueCare.

► **Messaging by the virtual coach platform to interact with other services:**

- **Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP)**, an open standard application layer protocol for message-orientation, queuing, routing, reliability, and security.

- **JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)**, a lightweight data-interchange format based on a subset of the JavaScript Programming Language Standard ECMA-262 3rd Edition - December 1999.
- **RabbitMQ**, the most widely deployed open-source message broker.
- **Firebase Cloud Messaging by Google**, a cross-platform messaging solution that provides reliable message delivery.

► **Communication:**

- **REST APIs** (also known as RESTful APIs), which conform to the constraints of REST architectural style and enable interaction with RESTful web services.
- Real-time communication for the web using WebRTC.

In summary, the ValueCare digital solution supports the use of industry-standard application interfaces or SDKs for communication between software and hardware components. This ensures maximum interoperability with third-party hardware. The architecture will support connections between the Virtual Coach and Vida24 and will facilitate the integration of activity tracker devices using either SDKs (such as Beurer AS 99) or APIs (for Xiaomi band devices).

4.4 Knowledge generated KERs

Why apply standards for the ValueCare Knowledge KERs?

Implementing standards for Knowledge KERs in ValueCare was crucial for several reasons. First and foremost, adherence to established standards ensured **consistency and uniformity** in the generation, documentation, and dissemination of knowledge-based outcomes. By adhering to recognised standards, ValueCare enhanced the credibility and reliability of their findings, thereby increasing trust among stakeholders and end-users.

Furthermore, applying standards provided a framework for organising and structuring knowledge-based results, making them **easier to understand, interpret, and use in different contexts**. This facilitates knowledge sharing and transfer not only within the consortium but also with external stakeholders, maximising the impact and utility of the projects Knowledge KERs.

Moreover, compliance with standards facilitated **interoperability and compatibility** with existing systems and practices, enabling seamless integration of the ValueCare results into broader initiatives. This interoperability ensured that the project's knowledge KERs can effectively contribute to larger-scale efforts and initiatives aimed at addressing VBHC.

Overall, applying standards for ValueCare results was crucial for promoting **transparency, rigor, and effectiveness** in the generation and utilisation of knowledge-based outcomes, ultimately enhancing the overall quality and impact of the project.

ValueCare Knowledge KERs and used existing standards

This section describes the Knowledge KERs of ValueCare and the standards in which their developments were based:

► Knowledge generated KER 1: Green Belt ValueCare Training programme

- **Development leader:** ISRAA
- **Outcome:** WP2
- **Description of the KER:** The training program seeks to provide a comprehensive approach to embracing VBHC. The Green Belt training intervention is designed to facilitate the integration of this model within the context of older adult care and among the adult population grappling with chronic illnesses.
- **Standards:** the development of the ValueCare Training programme was based on the 16 criteria collected in the following table (Table 10):

Table 10. Criteria of VBHC Program Certification

	Criteria
The VBHC philosophy of the program	Is the core idea of VBHC and the 4 VBHC implementation principles part of the program philosophy?
	Are the 8 core concepts of VBHC clearly part of the program philosophy and learning goals?
	Level of certification one star, two star (with exam online), three star (with support and defence of project/implementation)
The design, content & testing of participants method of the program	Are the 8 core concepts of VBHC implementation present in all parts of the program? (Patient relevant medical outcomes; patient involvement; defining the medical condition; IPC; measuring costs per full cycle of care; bundled payment contracts; IPU; learning cycles)
	Do the parts of the program include functional/practical tools to implement VBHC sufficiently? (Starting tools; patient pathways tools; measuring costs and reimbursement tools, technology tools; playbooks)
	Does the program contain the value agenda elements to help set course for participants to implement?
	Are challenges in information technology and data incorporated?
	Does the program take into account the perspective of different types of stakeholders involved in reforming healthcare? (Patients, providers, pharmaceuticals, payers, policy makers)
	Does the program have a base set of literature list for preparations and theoretical background?

	Is the program supplemented by certified successful implementation cases for discussion purposes?
	Is the program content current in terms of VBHC and not older than 2 years? And are the current VBHC cases or examples in the field incorporated?
Delivery model and pedagogy of the program	What are the program delivery, teaching methods, participant involvement and program management elements?
Evaluation of participants and improvement cycles	After 1-2 rounds of the program, what is the evaluation of the participants and if needed other stakeholders? How does the feedback and improvement of the program work? Have participants become ambassadors of the program?
Impact and review of the program	Are all the goals for the program met?
	Is the program still relevant?
	From a VBHC perspective, does the program tick all the boxes?

► **Knowledge generated KER 2: ValueCare VBHC Consultancy**

- **Development leader:** ISRAA
- **Outcome:** WP2
- **Description of the KER:** The VBHC consultancy provides an inclusive service aimed at certifying care units in accordance with the VBHC model. This service encompasses the use of the VBHC assessment toolkit, the Care Pathways redesign tool, and organisational shift planning.
- **Standards:** there are no standards about VBHC consultancy. Since there are no standards regarding exploitation/legal framework, we have developed the VBHC certification within the project, which will be described in D7.3.

► **Knowledge generated KER 3: ValueCare Co-creation methodology**

- **Development leader:** KVC
- **Outcome:** WP2
- **Description of the KER:** It is a methodology aimed to support the implementation of VBHC through the project implementation to feed the development of the VBHC concept and supportive digital solution with the active participation of end-users (older people, caregivers, health and social professionals, technological developers and health managers), through different activities: focus groups, interviews, World Café, etc.
- **Standards:** Although for the co-creation methodology of the ValueCare project no standards were used, it was based on the widely accepted DART Model (Dialogue, Access, Risk-benefits and Transparency). Developed by Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2004), the model aims to facilitate co-creation experiences between firms and consumers through four key elements: Dialog, Access, Transparency, and Assessment. Dialog involves interactivity, deep

engagement, and mutual willingness to act, requiring equality between partners for effective communication and joint problem-solving. Access and Transparency ensure that both parties have equal information, which, when combined with Dialog, allows for a clear Assessment of the risks and benefits of a given course of action.

Figure 3. Components of the DART model

Applying the DART model to ValueCare involved engaging the three target groups—older people and their families, health and social care practitioners, and managers—in co-creating the ValueCare concept and its technological solution (see D2.6 “Report on co-design activities for the ValueCare concept”). However, this process required refining the broader concept of “co-creation” into the more specific “co-design”, to align with the predicted collective creativity and design process involving primary, secondary, and tertiary end-users. This approach was focus not only on the ValueCare model and concept but also on the functional and technical features of the ValueCare digital tool. Co-design activities defined the concept of value from different target groups' perspectives on health and social care and identify the treatment pathways where ValueCare could provide benefits, and interaction between the target groups was further developed in later stages.

Moreover, co-creation methodology followed the key elements and recommendations of the “Code of practice on industry-academia co-creation of the EC⁷. Key elements were:

- Strategic approach. Industry and academia worked together in ValueCare to create an enabling environment for collaboration and actively seek for common interests and work together in research and innovation from early on.

⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/2e781f77-daa4-11ee-b9d9-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

- Matching supply and demand. Using brokers and digital platforms for matchmaking; interactive models for co-creation; support from infrastructures and co-creation facilities.
- Successful partnerships. Creating the right conditions for partnerships; professional support from intermediaries; effective valorisation of results; fair sharing of value created.

▶ **Knowledge generated KER 4: ValueCare Book**

- **Development leader:** ISRAA
- **Outcome:** WP2
- **Description of the KER:** The book "ValueCare Experience: A Pathway Towards a Value-Based Transition" serves as a comprehensive resource for individuals seeking guidance on transitioning to a VBHC model, leveraging the firsthand insights and experiences gained through the ValueCare project.
- **Standards:** no standards have been used for the development of the ValueCare Book.

▶ **Knowledge generated KER 5: Policy Recommendations**

- **Development leader:** UVEG
- **Outcome:** WP6
- **Description of the KER:** This document encompasses policy recommendations for scaling up ValueCare outcomes and provides guidelines on policies to promote the implementation of value-based integrated care at the regional or national level.
- **Standards:** For the development of policy recommendations, the project partners did not use any established standards. Instead, they relied on the knowledge extracted from the project and a comprehensive review of the needs and barriers in the provision of VBHC.

5 Conclusions

Deliverable 7.6 Report on the contribution to standardisation (end-term) complements the work carried out in D7.5, providing a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing the adoption and use of standards across project technological and knowledge-based KERs. The deliverable identifies and analyses the contribution of ValueCare to existing standards, and the contribution to the ongoing and future standardisation developments from its results. The report intends to clarify the significance of project results to standardisation in promoting innovation, interoperability and sustainability in health and ICT sectors. Moreover, the deliverable identifies the barriers and the final actions implemented towards standardisation.

1. **Contribution to existing standards:** ValueCare contributes to several existing standards with the technological KERs. Concretely, health and technological standards described in sections 4.3 and 4.4. In addition, the work done along the project implementation also contributes to existing instruments to measure health and, particularly, to the ICHOM dataset of older people. Although an active collaboration with the ICHOM organisation was not possible, partners presented in this deliverable some suggestions and will publish some papers with the results of the analysis made with the ICHOM set contributing to their validity in more languages, countries and populations (older people with comorbidities).
2. **New standards:** no new standards were provided in the current deliverable. However, guidelines and lessons learnt from the knowledge KERs are shared in this and other deliverables derived from the ValueCare project (such as D2.6, D3.2 and D3.4).

Thus, **the project achieves the committed KPI** of contributing to the “availability of valid instruments, able to improve the quality of life, life satisfaction, loneliness and social isolation” and is envisioned to also achieve the KPI on “Standardisation of cybersecurity and privacy protection technologies specifically for disruptive technologies based on massive data mining and analysis”.

Some **barriers** have been faced in the actions taken to contribute to standardisation within the project lifecycle:

- ▶ **Lack of awareness:** efforts to raise awareness among the consortium on how the project can contribute to standardisation were put in place to foster a common understanding on ValueCare contribution to standardisation. Dedicated meetings were organised by KVC to engage partners and increase the common understanding.
- ▶ **Complexity and bureaucracy of the standardisation process:** after conversations with UNE, it followed that the best process was a CWA for its simplicity and timeline. However, no consensus among partners was achieved on the results to be standardised in this form.

- ▶ Intellectual Property concerns: until the KERs and their exploitation responsibilities and rights among partners were not clear, the discussion about standardisation was difficult to include in the agenda.
- ▶ Lack of incentive structure or recognition: difficulties to recognise the added value to have a standard related to the project in addition to the normal deliverables, publications, results, etc.

As **lessons learnt**, partners would like to highlight the following:

- ▶ The inclusion of a dedicated task on standardisation forced partners to dedicate efforts to this issue and explore this new contribution of the project that otherwise would have remained unattended.
- ▶ The discussion of the potential contribution to standardisation, which took place from the very beginning of the project, was very useful to increase partners' knowledge in the field and open their minds to this new landscape.
- ▶ The HSbooster service was very useful to guide our work and better understand how research projects can contribute to existing and new standards.
- ▶ Although our conversations with relevant stakeholders were not successful in terms of tangible results, these contacts help us to define our work towards standardisation.

Finally, once this deliverable is approved by the European Commission, KVC will translate its content into a practical and editable format to be disseminated to the relevant audiences with the support of IFIC.

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Annex 1. STANDARDISATION Horizon Europe Booster Service

STANDARDISATION HSBOOSTER

26.04.2023 | 10.00h

<https://projectvaluecare.eu/>

PROJECT STATUS

- **Topic:** [Digital transformation in Health and Care \(H2020-SC1-DTH-2018-2020\)](#)
- eHealth, Well-Being and Ageing.
- **Objectives:**
 1. To deliver **integrated outcome-based care** to older people suffering from cognitive impairment, frailty and multiple chronic health conditions.
 2. To contribute to the **sustainability of health and social care systems in Europe**.
 3. To provide a secure, scalable and robust **digital solution for integrated care**.

Work Packages Overview

WP No.	Work Package Title	Lead Participant	Start Month	End month
1	Project Management	EMC	1	48
2	Development of new integrated care built on value-based methodology to be implemented at EU level	ISRAA	1	48
3	Digital IT for value-based integrated care	VI	3	48
4	VALUECARE pilots' implementation	MEDRI	12	40
5	Evaluation	EMC	3	48
6	Communication, dissemination and policy recommendations	IFIC	1	48
7	Exploitation, innovation and business models	ECHA	3	48
8	Ethics and data protection	UVEG	1	48
9	Ethics requirements	EMC	1	48

WP7 Framework

Standardisation

How the work done in ValueCare project can contribute to existing standards?

- Use of the **ICHOM set** to assess patient-reported outcome measures among older people with various chronic conditions;
- Implementation of a **personalized care plan** by integrating standard measures from the medical and social domain;
- **Exchange of data** through the ValueCare technical solution

Is ValueCare providing new potential standards?

- The vision of ValueCare is to support **data exchange** by using common terminology and common data models. By applying this in the project, ValueCare can be seen as a 'use case'. It could be that standards are improved or that there is a need for new standards. However, we need to evaluate this first

Standardisation

Digital Solution

Is the ValueCare digital solution contributing to digital transition? If yes, how?

Yes. It contributes to digital transition by enabling a series of actions that otherwise would not be possible such as:

- **increased accessibility to healthcare services regarding time and location** (i.e. continuous access to people in rural environments or distant to care facilities).
- **Improved patient outcomes**, through longitudinal monitoring, personalised recommendations and continuous collection of patients data accessible to care professionals
- **Increased engagement and awareness**, by empowering patients to take an active role in their healthcare management through the use of the digital tools
- **Improving the digital literacy**, through the experiencing and use of the digital tools for health

Standardisation

Digital Solution

Is the ValueCare digital solution able to be connected/integrated with other solutions/products?

- Yes. Being developed in three main modules (the web dashboard, the mobile app and the virtual coach engine), the ValueCare system and its components could be interfaced to other solutions and products to enhance its potential use. Moreover, the ValueCare app is highly configurable to tackle other clinical conditions beyond the ones defined within the project pilots.

Is the ValueCare digital solution following existing standards? (i.e. AI, security)

- Yes. The design of the digital solution follows the accessibility and security standards such as the ones implemented in the Vidavo dashboard. Moreover, the virtual coach is designed in a compatible way with the approach defined by **FHIR for healthcare data exchange**.

Usable Knowledge and exploitable results

TECHNICAL

- Technical solutions for patient management and patient empowerment
- Value-based Digital Solution (a Cloud SaaS, as an ecosystem including the ancillary services)
- Virtual Coach (solution component)
- ValueCare App (solution component)
- Webservice (solution component)

Usable Knowledge and exploitable results

NEW KNOWLEDGE

- Virtual Coach usage data (to inform new Machine Learning algorithms and or to be correlated with users' health technology readiness.
- Co-creation methodology (relevant for other digital health innovators)
- Data sets implemented (not part of ICHOM or other standards)
- ValueCare Care Model & Care pathway methodology (coaching, training, framework evaluation)
- Educational and training material (*the book - ValueCare experience: a pathway towards a ValueBased transition*)

ROADMAP TO STANDARDISATION

1. Internal Webinar + Workshop in Athens

Focusing on what would be exploitable and standardise by the consortium.

Strategic motivation from partners

2. HSBooster (Horizon Standardisation Booster) – ValueCare already accepted for the service: SGS Brightside / TrustIT providers.

- Meet standardisation experts
- Plan contributions to WPs
- Learn about the standards landscape
- Improvement of skillset and strategy

3. 1st meeting with UNE (Spanish Association for Standardisation)

